

3D CHARACTERISATION OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURE VIA X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

S. Sommacal¹, A. Kingston², M. Ploeckl³, A. Matschinski³, P. Consul³, M. Saadatfar², and P. Compston¹

¹ ARC Training Centre for Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites, Research School of Electrical Energy and Materials Engineering, The Australian National University, Canberra, Australia, silvano.sommacal@anu.edu.au

² Research School of Physical Sciences and Engineering, The Australian National University, Canberra, Australia

³ Chair of Carbon Composites, Technical University of Munich, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Garching, Germany,

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite materials possess highly desirable physical and chemical properties and are now commonly utilized in many structural components in aerospace, civil engineering, military, as well as in motorsports and other competition sports.

Structural defects in CFRPs are often caused by insufficient fibre impregnation and non-optimized process parameters during the manufacturing process. These defects can severely compromise the expected performance from CFRPs [1], [2]. Understanding the characteristic geometry and shape of these defects as well as their spatial distribution within the three-dimensional (3D) CFRP's structure (matrix and fibres) can provide insight into the origin of their formation and can enable optimization of the fabrication process.

In this study, a state-of-art 3D X-ray microscopy technique by computed-tomography (micro-CT), combined with tomographic volume analysis and visualization tools, has been utilized to study a suite of highly different CFRPs. Using both proprietary and open-source software, the main constituent materials (fibres, matrix/resin, voids) of the samples have been identified and segmented; the distribution of each material is then mapped in 3D and the respective volume fractions are quantified. As a case study, segmented voids have been clustered into two different families based on their shape and preferential location within the material micro-structure of one particular sample.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are characterised by advantageous and desirable properties such as: high stiffness and tensile strength; low weight; high chemical resistance and temperature tolerance; excellent durability; and design flexibility. These properties have led to composite materials becoming widely used across a variety of industries in recent years. At the same time, it is well known that commonly encountered material structural defects can cause large variations in a material mechanical performance [1], [2]. These defects can include voids, fibre misalignment, formation/propagation of cracks within the matrix and delaminations at the interface between different layers. Process induced voids are probably the most common micro-structural defect to be found in CFRPs and their presence alone can have detrimental effects to a variety of material properties including: interlaminar shear strength, flexural and compressive properties (strength and modulus), fracture toughness, and fatigue resistance [3].

The 3D visualization and investigation of the internal geometry of a material coupled with the detailed analysis of its micro-structure to identify, assess and quantify voids and other structural

defects, are therefore essential in order to facilitate the design and manufacturing of more reliable and robust CFRP products. Several image-based approaches to characterize and analyse the distribution of voids and fibres within a composite structure have been proposed. Using optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), 2D high resolution images of voids and individual fibres can be acquired in a destructive way [4]. SEM based X-ray ultra-microscopy systems can acquire high resolution 3D images but only for a very small specimen due to the low energy (30keV max) of the X-rays produced and since the specimen is placed in a vacuum chamber they cannot easily accommodate experimental rigs [5].

More recently micro-CT has gained popularity as a non-destructive inspection technique that provides high-resolution, high-quality, structural 3D information to investigate the heterogeneity and architecture of several different types of composite materials [6]. Using this technique, internal structural features and manufacturing defects for various types of composites can be characterised and quantified and their influence and impact on the material's expected performance better understood [1].

In this work that has benefited from the most recent advances made at the Australian National University (ANU) in the field of high-resolution large-angle cone-beam micro-CT scanning and image reconstruction techniques [7], [8], we used X-ray micro-CT to acquire volume data and probe the 3D microstructure of our composite samples and subsequently derive relevant sets of structural and geometrical parameters directly from the tomograms.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Cone-beam X-ray Computed Tomography

Lab-based cone-beam micro-CT is a fine-focus system for 3D microscopy that comprises an X-ray source, a sample manipulation stage and an X-ray detector. It provides lensless (i.e. optics-free) geometrical magnification through the spherical propagation of X-rays from the micro-focus source. Using this system, a specimen is not directly imaged in 3D, rather, volumetric data is obtained by reconstructing the object that is consistent with a series of 2D projection images (or radiographs) of the specimen obtained from different viewing angles. In the majority of commercial micro-CT instruments in use today, the set of viewing angles of the 2D radiographs are acquired using a circular X-ray source scanning trajectory about the sample. The tomographic volume is then reconstructed using the analytically-derived, filtered back-projection (FBP) algorithm developed by Feldkamp-Davis-Kress [9]. However, a circular trajectory does not satisfy the Tuy data sufficiency condition for cone-beam reconstruction [10]. The reconstruction is approximate and it is commonly recognized that the FDK technique produces acceptable results only for cone-angles less than $\pm 5^\circ$. The left image of Figure 1 demonstrates the effects of this approximation beyond 5° with artefacts appearing. Since a micro-focus X-ray source usually produces a near-isotropic flux of X-rays in all forward directions, the low-angle cone-beam geometry required for circular scanning means only a small fraction of these X-rays are captured and utilized.

Figure 1: Vertical slice through a Defrise-Clack phantom comprised of horizontal plates. Volume reconstructed through 32 iterations of the conjugate gradient method. Left: circular scanning trajectory with cone-angle $\pm 5^\circ$; right: a low-pitch helix scanning trajectory with cone-angle $\pm 45^\circ$.

In tomography, X-ray photons contain and carry the useful information and the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in an image is entirely due to finite photon numbers; the more photons collected the better. A helical rather than circular scanning trajectory represents an ideal trajectory that satisfies the Tuy condition and enables theoretically-exact tomographic reconstruction. It allows high-fidelity imaging and makes use of a high-cone-angle geometry. The right image of Figure 1 demonstrates the benefits of satisfying the Tuy condition and this data would collect 16x more X-ray flux than the circular trajectory on the left. Since 2010, micro-CT instruments developed and built at the ANU [7] have been utilizing a helical trajectory combined with a FBP algorithm developed by Katsevich [11]. Although the Katsevich reconstruction formula is theoretically-exact it is also known to be affected by artefacts caused by imperfections in the acquisition trajectory. To address this issue an automated system has been developed [12] and implemented in all the ANU micro-CT instruments that corrects for imperfections in the acquisition trajectory allowing for accurate reconstruction at cone-beam angles exceeding $\pm 35^\circ$ (i.e. full cone angle $\sim 70^\circ$). This larger cone-angle yields a far better utilization of the available X-ray flux (more than 40 times higher than an equivalent circular scan) improving dramatically the image SNR for a given experiment time and leading to shorter image acquisition time.

More recently some important shortcomings linked to the utilization of helical trajectories have been revealed; among them, the non-uniformity of resolution within the tomogram, a problem that could be reduced by adopting a double-helix or a low-pitch helix trajectory at the cost, however, of an increase in data redundancy and scanning time [11], [13]. Most recent advances made at the ANU towards the production of high-resolution high-fidelity tomograms from large cone beam computed tomography datasets have led to the utilization in all the micro-CT instruments of a new family of X-ray source scanning trajectory, the space-filling trajectory (SFT) [8]. SFT represents a discrete path through space, rather than continuous like for circular or helical trajectories, that is generated using a low-discrepancy sequence of strides along a low-pitch helical path and which uniformly samples the entire space of possible source positions. In the work of Kingston et al. [8] it is numerically demonstrated that SFT allows for the most isotropic sampling of the data, providing as uniform resolution as possible, satisfies the Tuy data sufficiency condition and requires minimal filtering of the measured data, minimizing as a result data redundancy. In addition, Kingston et al. [8] showed that the adoption of SFT decreases data acquisition time and improves image quality by reducing reconstruction artefacts. Computationally efficient iterative reconstruction schemes, instead of analytical reconstruction, have also been developed at ANU [14]. These are an optimisation based reconstruction; they try to find the object that best matches the measured data when projected by the forward process that simulates the experiment. Reconstructions can become more quantitative since physical processes such as sample motion, X-ray beam hardening, can be incorporated.

2.2 Image acquisition, processing and analysis

All images utilised for this work have been acquired using the SFT at the ANU CT lab on a micro-CT instrument equipped with a flat panel detector with 3040 x 3040 pixels and a micro-focus X-ray source of 60 kV. Inside the micro-CT chamber, the specimens were placed on a motor controlled rotating stage and radioscope projections were taken after each interval of rotation. Subsequently, the grayscale projections were processed to reconstruct full 3D digital composites geometry using proprietary ANU Helical Reconstruction software [15]. The scanning resolution (i.e. voxel size) of the images acquired varied between 1.1 and 1.6 μm and the total acquisition time between 10 and 26 hours per scan, which warranted for the acquisition of high quality (i.e. high signal-to-noise ratio) scans.

All the reconstructed 3D images, created as grey scale 16 bits netCDF data files, were first qualitatively analyzed (i.e. visually inspected) using an open-source netCDF viewer. This procedure allowed to evaluate the overall quality of the images, identify and investigate possible artefacts affecting them, assess their impact on image quality and decide whether and what image enhancement procedure should have been performed to further improve image quality. It also let to identify the type and number of different phases that in each of the images could be distinguished and potentially segmented.

Image processing and quantitative analysis were then carried out using Mango, the software tool for image enhancement, parallel segmentation and network generation developed at the ANU specifically to work with tomographic data. The image segmentation process we employed is based on the method developed by Sheppard et al. [16], that combines active contours, where an initial region is chosen and then its boundary evolves depending on the grey-scale image intensity, gradient, interfacial curvature and geodetic distance from the nearest edge, with bottom-up watershed finding schemes, where the image gradient is thought as a landscape and within it regions are seeded at local topographic minima and then two interfaces grow towards each other until they meet at the watershed. With this segmentation method, the introduction of a speed function governing the rate at which the interfaces approach each other allows to use in any chosen combination all information available on the grey-scale image intensity and gradient.

For selected sections/portions of the samples, micro-CT volumetric data was then rendered in 3D using Drishti [17].

3 MATERIALS

Three very different types of carbon fibre reinforced polymers have been utilized for this work:

1. A sandwich structure of foam with CF-reinforced epoxy top and bottom layers. One cylindrical sample of approximately 2 mm diameter and 6.5 mm length was cored using a thin-wall diamond core drill, and then imaged by micro-CT (26 hours scan, 1.3 μm voxel size image).
2. A unidirectional CF-reinforced PEEK composite laminate manufactured using a near-infrared laser automated fibre placement (AFP) system at the Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany. The laminate is around 4 mm thick and has been manufactured at a placement speed of 3 m/min. One cylindrical sample of ~ 2 mm diameter was cored, using the same drill as for the sandwich structure, perpendicular to the fibres direction, and then imaged by micro-CT (16 hours scan, 1.3 μm voxel size image).
3. A 3D printed sample produced at TUM on an Apium P220 industrial 3D printer utilizing as feedstock a commercial high-performance CF/PEEK material containing 30% by weight of carbon fibre fragments randomly distributed within the matrix. The sample was produced as a stack of layers by setting the printing parameters as follow:
 - 0,1 mm individual layer height
 - 0,4 mm individual layer width
 - 510°C extrusion temperature
 - 95% extrusion multiplierOne specimen, $\sim 2 \times 2$ mm square cross-section and ~ 6 mm length, was imaged by micro-CT (10 hours scan, 1.6 μm voxel size image).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Images acquired on the three different CF reinforced samples have been thoroughly investigated and for each of the 3D volumes the material micro-structure analysed and characterised. Main material's constituents, i.e. voids (very low-to-no X-ray attenuation, hence dark grey to black colour in the tomogram image), matrix (mid X-ray attenuation, intermediate grey colour) and fibres (higher X-ray attenuation, brighter colour) have been identified and mapped in 3D. When possible and meaningful, voids unusual / heterogeneous distribution and clustering have been highlighted and their association with specific material microstructural features analysed and mapped in 3D. For each of the 3D images, fibres, matrix and manufacturing defects such as voids and cracks have been segmented and their individual total amounts quantified in volume %. In addition, for the laminate sample, segmented voids have been further clustered into two different families depending on their shape, rounded / sub-rounded or elongated, and preferential location with respect to matrix and fibres.

4.1 Sandwich Structure

The sandwich structure is clearly visible in the 3D grayscale tomogram image shown to the left of Figure 2. A visual inspection of the image revealed that both the top and bottom CF rich portions are made of epoxy reinforced with multidirectional fibres bundles and are both characterised by the presence of voids of various sizes, with generally a rounded / sub-rounded shape and mostly located in epoxy rich areas. In addition, the presence of a small quantity of a higher density (HD) material of uncertain origin, although probably some sort of contamination, could also be identified.

Given their similarity, we decided to carry out quantitative analysis on only one between the top and bottom portions, and arbitrary chose to focus on the top section. As a first step in the image processing, we digitally extracted from the top portion of the sandwich structure the image volume containing only useful data (i.e. no foam), while masking everything else out. In Figure 2, the image in the centre represents a 3D visualisation of a vertical slice through the selected top section of the tomogram image shown to the left. In this image, different multidirectional bundles of fibres can be clearly distinguished together with some resin rich areas and a number of voids. We then segmented the constituent phases (fibres, epoxy, voids and HD material), mapped their distribution in 3D and quantified respective individual total amounts as volume %. In Figure 2, the image to the right represents a 3D visualisation of the segmented image obtained from Figure 2-centre showing the distribution in 3D of voids (cyan colour) and small speckles of HD material (white), while fibres and epoxy are set to transparent / semi-transparent. Results of the segmentation analysis carried out on the selected top portion of the image are summarised in Table 1.

Figure 2: 3D visualisations from tomogram (left and centre) grey-scale and segmented (right) binary images of the sandwich structure; see text for more detailed explanation. Field of view (FOV), left image: ~6.5 (length) x 2 (diameter) mm; centre and right: ~2 (diameter) x 1 (thickness) mm.

Voids	Resin	Fibres	HD
0.46	50.36	49.13	0.05

Table 1: Results expressed as volume % of the segmentation process carried out on the top section of the sandwich structure tomographic image.

4.2 Unidirectional Carbon-Fibre Reinforced PEEK Laminate

Visual inspection of the 3D tomogram image revealed that spatial distribution and density of the unidirectional fibres is not entirely homogeneous throughout the CF-PEEK laminate sample analysed and within its microstructure there are relatively large areas / volumes which are made predominantly of resin. In Figure 3, the image to the left represents a 3D visualisation of two vertical slices digitally extracted from the laminate cylindrical specimen tomogram image in a direction approximately perpendicular / parallel to the main carbon fibres orientation and which allow to appreciate in detail the sample microstructure. In these 3D images areas of intermediate grey colour encompassing very little-to-none of the brighter phase (i.e. fibres), identify portions within the image with very low carbon fibres density and made predominantly of resin that usually appear in the form of thin layers randomly distributed throughout the sample and mostly oriented parallel to the main fibres direction. Furthermore, a minor although widespread fibres misalignment could be recognised, with individual fibres occasionally having what would appear to be a totally random orientation and / or being broken. Finally, voids (very dark grey to black colour in Figure 3-left) of different size and shape are also clearly present.

We then performed a quantitative analysis on the whole volume data imaged by segmenting the three material's main constituents: fibres, resin and voids. During the segmentation process, we had to account for the image sharpening artefact caused by *x-ray refraction* [18] that predominantly affected our image analysis by causing a higher density halo to be present around the voids. These halos have a two to three micron cross-sectional diameter and are characterised by an average grey intensity value very close to that of the fibres, while they instead occupy regions mostly made of resin. An example of halos encountered in our image processing is shown in Figure 4-top left. The same slice has been shown in the top-right after Paganin X-ray phase retrieval [19] was performed to undo refraction effects. Here we assumed a mean X-ray energy of 30keV and the ratio of $\beta/\Delta = 0.0003$ where the refractive index is defined as $n = 1 - \Delta + i\beta$. Results show that this halo is indeed an imaging artefact and not a physical feature in the tomogram. To prevent the incorrect 3D mapping of the fibres and overestimation of their volume content, we designed an automatic image processing procedure that first isolated all regions around the voids initially segmented as fibres and then re-assigned most of them to the matrix phase. A schematic example of the procedure followed in dealing with the *x-ray refraction effect* artefact is shown in Figure 4; while shown in Figure 3, centre and right, are two 3D visualisations of segmented images for the same tomogram vertical slices of Figure 3-left.

The information we gained from the segmentation and 3D mapping of the voids on their size, shape, location and distribution was then used to further segment and cluster them into two separate categories based mostly on their shape and preferential location: A) rounded / sub-rounded, generally bigger although less common, mostly located in resin rich areas and likely to represent air bubbles trapped within the matrix during the manufacturing process, and B) thin and elongated, mostly located between fibres and likely to represent tight areas where the resin did not penetrate. An example of the two different families of voids and how they have been separated is shown in Figure 5.

Final segmentation results are summarised in Table 2, which includes the calculated volume percentage for voids type A and B showing that each represents about 10 and 90%, respectively, of the total amount of segmented voids.

Figure 3: 3D visualization of the CF-PEEK laminate micro-CT scan. Left: tomogram image; centre: correspondent 3-phase segmented image with fibres shown in orange, matrix in grey, voids in blue; right: segmented image showing only voids after fibres and matrix are made 100 % transparent. FOV: ~ 3.2 (length) x 2 (diameter) mm.

Figure 4: Small subsets images (FOV: $\sim 130 \times 300 \mu\text{m}$, $10 \mu\text{m}$ thickness) where, top left: tomogram image showing high density halos wrapped around voids and carbon fibres (CF) having very similar grey intensity values; top right: same image after applying Paganin phase retrieval [19] demonstrating that halos are imaging artefacts; bottom left: halos are initially segmented as 'fibres'; bottom right: halos are removed from fibres phase and re-assigned to matrix phase.

Figure 5: Small cylindrical volume images (FOV: ~ 2 mm diameter, $22 \mu\text{m}$ thickness) showing, left: tomogram image; right: corresponding segmented image after voids clustering into type A (green colour) and B (red), with matrix set 100% transparent and fibres semi-transparent.

Voids (total)	Matrix	Fibres	Voids (A)*	Voids (B)*
1.95	65.86	32.18	0.19	1.67

Table 2: Segmentation results in volume % for the 3D volume of the laminate sample analysed.

*Voids smaller than $100 \mu^3$ were removed before separating them into A and B, lowering their total amount to 1.86%.

4.3 3D printed sample

Qualitative analysis of the 3D tomogram image shown in Figure 6-left, revealed the presence of a large quantity of voids of various size, from very small to quite large, and mostly irregular shape that appear to be preferentially aligned in rows along the printing direction. It is also clear that the voids distribution is not homogeneous within the 3D volume imaged with their amount to be lowest near the mould plate and progressively increasing moving away along the direction perpendicular to that surface.

In our image processing, we initially performed a two-phase segmentation, where phase 0 = voids, phase 1 = fibres + resin, on the whole volume imaged. This allowed us to map the voids distribution in 3D and quantify their total amount as volume %. We then digitally split the image into three equal size sub-volumes, *bot*, *mid*, *top*, as shown in Figure 6, where *bot* represents the sub-volume located closer to the mould plate and *top* the furthest, and computed the voids content for each of them. Results of our segmentation, summarised in Table 3, confirmed the strongly heterogeneous distribution of the voids.

As next step in our quantitative analysis, we segmented the fibres fragments for the whole volume imaged, mapped their 3D distribution and quantified their total amount as volume %. The fibres segmentation image processing was in this case guided and constrained by prior compositional information available on the feedstock material. We know that the CF/PEEK composite material utilised to produce this sample contains 30% by weight of carbon fibres (w_f), hence 70% by weight of matrix (w_m), and we can safely assume that fibres content would not be lost during the printing process. Since we also know the density values of both carbon fibres ($\rho_f = 1.79 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and matrix ($\rho_m = 1.3 \text{ g/cm}^3$), we can calculate the average composite material density (ρ_c) from:

$$\rho_c = 1/[(w_f/\rho_f)+(w_m/\rho_m)] = 1.42 \text{ g/cm}^3 \text{ [20]} \quad (1)$$

The average composite density value can then be used to calculate the content of fibres expressed as volume % (v_f), using:

$$v_f = (\rho_c/\rho_f)*w_f = 23.74\% \text{ [20]} \quad (2)$$

This would be the fibres content for a material composed entirely by fibres and resin (i.e. no voids), while taking into account the presence in the sample of 19.1% voids, as obtained in our two-phase segmentation, we derive that the fibres content for the whole 3D volume must be 19.2%, hence the total resin content 61.7%.

The printed sample tomogram image was affected by an *x-ray refraction effect* artefact, causing the presence of high density halos wrapped around the voids, very similar to what we encountered within the laminate image. During the fibres segmentation image processing we dealt with this artefact in an analogous way as described in section 4.2. In Figure 6, centre and right, are shown some segmented images for the whole 3D printed sample, while shown in Figure 7 are some tomogram and segmented images for three subsets extracted each from one of the *bot*, *mid* and *top*, sub-volumes.

Results of the segmentation process are given in Table 3. The segmented total amount of fibres calculated on the whole 3D volume analysed is 19.1%, which is very close to the theoretically correct value of 19.2%. Segmented fibres and matrix contents for each of the three sub-volumes (*bot*, *mid*, *top*) are also reported in Table 3.

Figure 6: Drishti visualisations of the 3D printed sample tomogram (left) and segmented (centre and right) images. Segmented image in the centre shows matrix (grey colour) and fibres (orange) while voids are made 100% transparent; segmented image to the right shows matrix and voids (blue) while fibres are made 100% transparent. The three sub-volumes *bot*, *mid*, *top*, are also identified in the images. FOV: ~6 (length) x 2 x 2 (cross-section) mm for all images.

Figure 7: Tomogram (right column) and segmented images for three subsets digitally extracted from approximately the middle of bot, mid and top sub-volumes. For each of the subsets, next to the tomogram image is a 3-phase segmented image (colour scheme same as Figure 6), then the same image with voids made 100% transparent and, left column, with matrix 100% transparent. FOV: ~ 1.3 (depth), 1.5×0.5 (cross-section) mm for all images.

	Whole	Bot	Mid	Top
Voids	19.1	11.6	20.7	25.7
Fibres	19.1	17.4	20.2	19.0
Resin	61.8	71.0	59.1	55.3

Table 3: Segmentation results for the whole 3D printed sample and each of the three sub-volumes analysed in this work.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A sandwich structure of foam with CF-reinforced epoxy top and bottom layers, a unidirectional CF-PEEK laminate and a CF-PEEK 3D printed sample, have been analysed by micro-CT in this work, that took advantage of the latest improvements in the field of scanning and image reconstruction techniques made at the ANU.

For each of the materials high-quality high-resolution images have been acquired and then investigated in detail to probe their 3D microstructure. Manufacturing defects, such as voids, locally insufficient fibres impregnation and/or misalignment, heterogeneous fibres density and/or voids distribution, have been identified and analysed. Using advanced image processing techniques, fibres, matrix/resin and voids have been segmented, their volume fractions quantified and distribution mapped in 3D.

For the unidirectional laminate, voids have been furthered separated into two different types, which could each be associated to a different issue during the manufacturing process. The 3D printed sample was shown to have a highly heterogeneous distribution of voids and fibres that has been analysed in detail, visualised in 3D and quantified.

This work will provide the basis for future studies aiming at quantifying the impact of the mapped defects, voids and fibres misalignment in particular, on the material's properties and mechanical performance that will ultimately enable optimization of the manufacturing process for this kind of materials.

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REFERENCES

- [1] I. Baran, I. Straumit, O. Shishkina, and S. V. Lomov, X-ray computed tomography characterization of manufacturing induced defects in a glass/polyester pultruded profile, *Composite Structures*, 195, 2018, pp. 74-82.
- [2] C. Dong, Effects of Process-Induced Voids on the Properties of Fibre Reinforced Composites, *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, 32, 2018, pp. 597-604.
- [3] A. Scott, I. Sinclair, S. Spearing, M. Mavrogordato and W. Hepples, Influence of voids on damage mechanisms in carbon/epoxy composites determined via high resolution computed tomography, *Composites Science and Technology*, 90, 2014, pp. 147-153.
- [4] K. Gall, M. Mikulas, N.A. Munshi, F. Beavers, M. Tupper, Carbon Fiber Reinforced Shape Memory Polymer Composites, *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, 11, 2000, pp. 877-886.
- [5] S. Mayo, T. Davis, T. Gureyev, P. Miller, D. Paganin, A. Pogany, A. Stevenson and S. Wilkins, X-ray phase-contrast microscopy and microtomography, *Optics Express*, 11, 2003, pp. 2289-2302.
- [6] S.C. Garcea, Y. Wang, and P.J. Withers, X-ray computed tomography of polymer composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, 156, 2018, pp. 305-319.
- [7] T. Varslot, A. Kingston, G. Myers and A. Sheppard, High-resolution helical cone-beam micro-CT with theoretically-exact reconstruction from experimental data, *Medical physics*, 38, 2011, pp. 5459-5476.
- [8] A. Kingston, G. Myers, S. Latham, B. Recur, H. Li and A. Sheppard, Space-filling X-ray source trajectories for efficient scanning in large-angle cone-beam computed tomography, *IEEE Transactions on Computational Imaging*, 4, 2018, pp.447-458.
- [9] L. Feldkamp, L. Davis and J. Kress, Practical cone-beam algorithm, *Journal of the Optical Society of America A*, 1, 1984, pp. 612-619.

- [10] H. Tuy, An inverse formula for cone-beam reconstruction, *SIAM Journal on Applied Mathematics*, 43, 1983, pp. 546–552.
- [11] A. Katsevich, 3PI algorithms for helical computer tomography, *Advances in Applied Mathematics*, 36, 2006, pp. 213-250.
- [12] A. Kingston, A. Sakellariou, T. Varslot, G. Myers, and A. Sheppard, Reliable automatic alignment of tomographic projection data by passive auto-focus, *Medical physics*, 38, 2011, pp. 4934-4945.
- [13] T. Varslot, A. Kingston, G. Myers and A. Sheppard, Considerations for high-magnification high-cone-angle helical micro-CT, *Proceedings of the SPIE Optical Engineering + Applications Conference on Developments in X-Ray Tomography VIII, San Diego, California, United States, October 17, 2012*, Vol. 8506, 2012, Art. No. 850614.
- [14] G. Myers, A. Kingston, S. Latham, B. Recur, T. Li, M. Turner, L. Beeching and A. Sheppard, Rapidly converging multigrid reconstruction of cone-beam tomographic data, *Proceedings of the SPIE Optical Engineering + Applications Conference on Developments in X-Ray Tomography X, San Diego, California, United States, October 3, 2016*, Vol. 9967, 2016, Art. No. 99671M.
- [15] A. Sheppard, S. Latham, J. Middleton, A. Kingston, G. Myers, T. Varslot, A. Fogden, T. Sawkins, R. Cruikshank, M. Saadatfar, N. Francois, C. Arns and T. Senden, Techniques in helical scanning, dynamic imaging and image segmentation for improved quantitative analysis with X-ray micro-CT, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 324, 2014, pp. 49-56.
- [16] A. Sheppard, R. Sok and H. Averdunk, Techniques for image enhancement and segmentation of tomographic images of porous materials, *Physica A: Statistical mechanics and its applications*, 339, 2004, pp. 145-151.
- [17] A. Limaye, Drishti: a volume exploration and presentation tool, *Proceedings of the SPIE Optical Engineering + Applications Conference on Developments in X-Ray Tomography VIII, San Diego, California, United States, October 17, 2012*, Vol. 8506, 2012, Art. No. 85060X.
- [18] S. Wilkins, T. Gureyev, D. Gao, A. Pogany and A. Stevenson, Phase-contrast imaging using polychromatic hard X-rays, *Nature*, 384, 1996, pp. 335-337.
- [19] D. Paganin, S. Mayo, T. Gureyev, P. Miller and S. Wilkins, Simultaneous phase and amplitude extraction from a single defocused image of a homogeneous object, *Journal of Microscopy*, 206, 2002, pp. 33-40.
- [20] R. Gibson, *Principles of Composite Material Mechanics*, Mechanical Engineering, Vol. 218, CRC Press Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, 2012.